

Supplementary Materials for the article
“Comparing internet and phone survey mode
effects across countries and research contexts”

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Appendix

Additional econometric details for WTP model

We specify each respondent i 's indirect utility representation for two cases for each outage scenario $s \in \{1 \dots S\}$: in the event of a power outage with the characteristics stipulated by s denoted as \tilde{v}_{is}^* , and in the event that they pay to avoid such an outage denoted as \tilde{v}_{is} .

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{v}_{is}^* &= \gamma_i m_i - d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + d_s \tilde{\epsilon}_{is} \\ \tilde{v}_{is} &= \gamma_i (m_i - P_{is}) + d_s \tilde{\epsilon}_{i0}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Where m_i is the household income of respondent i , P_{is} is the bid price entered as a positive number, \mathbf{x}'_{is} are observed respondent and scenario characteristics, and d_s is the outage duration measured in hours. We can show the model in “utility-space” by subtracting the above two utilities.

$$v_{is}^* = \tilde{v}_{is} - \tilde{v}_{is}^* = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \gamma_i P_{is} + d_s (\tilde{\epsilon}_{i0} - \tilde{\epsilon}_{is})\tag{2}$$

We elect to estimate this model in WTP space for ease of interpretation and improved credibility of the results, as shown by Train and Weeks (2005) and Sonnier et al. (2007). Thus, we divide through the previous equation by the marginal utility of income γ_i . This yields v_{is} which can be interpreted as the difference between the full WTP to avoid the outage in menu s and P_{is} . The

model is then written as:

$$v_{is} = \frac{v_{is}^*}{\gamma_i} = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta} - P_{is} + d_s \kappa_{is},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{is} &= \frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}^*}{\gamma_i}, \\ \kappa_{is} &= \frac{(\tilde{\epsilon}_{i0} - \tilde{\epsilon}_{is})}{\gamma_i} \quad \text{where} \quad \kappa_{is} = \alpha_i + \epsilon_{is}, \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

with

$$\alpha_i \sim N(0, \delta_\alpha^2), \quad \epsilon_{is} \sim N(0, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2),$$

where we split the error term into within-respondent and between-respondent segments, so we can estimate the random effect term α_i for each respondent. For a vector of observed binary choice responses, \mathbf{y}_i , a response of 1 will be observed when $v_{is} > 0$. The hierarchical structure of the model suggests a Bayesian approach, in which the conditional likelihood $p(y_{is} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2)$ is combined with the distribution of the variances within respondents, $p(\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 | w)$, and with the distributions of the common parameters $p(\delta_\alpha^2 | \mathbf{h})$ and $p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \mathbf{g})$. We select an inverted Gamma distribution for $\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2$, such that $\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 \sim IG(r, \varrho)$. r is chosen as fixed parameter, such that ϱ remains an unknown hyperparameter and follows a second-stage prior distribution $p(\varrho | \mathbf{q})$.

The joint posterior distribution is then given by

$$p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{1,\epsilon}^2, \dots, \delta_{N,\epsilon}^2, \varrho | \mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N, \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{h}, r, \mathbf{q}) \propto \prod_i p(\mathbf{y}_{is} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2) p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \mathbf{g}) p(\delta_\alpha^2 | \mathbf{h}) p(\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 | r, \varrho) p(\varrho | \mathbf{q}) \quad (4)$$

We select a Gamma distribution as prior of ϱ , giving

$$\varrho \sim G(a_\varrho, A_\varrho), \quad (5)$$

and likewise select a inverted Gamma distribution as prior of the variance between respondents, such that

$$\delta_\alpha^2 \sim IG(a_{\delta_\alpha^2}, A_{\delta_\alpha^2}). \quad (6)$$

For the common parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ we define a normal prior,

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} \sim N(\mathbf{a}_\beta, \mathbf{A}_\beta). \quad (7)$$

The resulting full conditional posterior distributions are standard in Bayesian econometric literature (Rossi et al., 2005). We draw from the posterior via a Gibbs Sampler. The final model output is 20,000 draws of each estimable parameter, with 10,000 of these draws as burn-in. Using these parameter draws we then calculate the mean WTP in table ?? to avoid an hour of power outage

for each respondent-scenario observation as $v_{is} + P_{is} = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta} + d_s (\alpha_i + \epsilon_{is})$, and setting $d_s = 1$. The draws of the random effect term α_i are used following Campbell (2007). This is an in-sample calculation which loops over all 10,000 usable draws of each parameter and all 61,928 observations (7,741 respondents with 8 choices per respondent). This results in 10,000 draws from an empirical distribution of WTP for each observation. These draws are summarized by country to yield the results in table ??.

Additional econometric details for the Ordered Probit model

The ordered probit model, as specified in equation 8, is motivated by a continuous, unobserved latent variable y_i^* that exists for each individual i . In this case it is useful to think of y_i^* as respondent i 's perceived change in indirect utility due to the development. The respondent then selects DYA and PYA, for higher values of y_i^* , and PNA or DNA for lower values of y_i^* . Survey answers are the *observed response*, which we denote as y_i . The latent variable y_i^* maps the observed response, such that if y_i^* falls between two

thresholds y_i takes a certain value. This is shown in equation 8.

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_i^* &= \mathbf{X}_i\boldsymbol{\beta} + \epsilon_i \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, 1) \\
 y_i &= 1(\text{DNA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad y_i^* \leq v_1 \\
 y_i &= 2(\text{PNA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad v_1 < y_i^* \leq v_2 \\
 y_i &= 3(\text{PYA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad v_2 < y_i^* \leq v_3 \\
 y_i &= 4(\text{DYA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad y_i^* \geq v_3,
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is a vector of slope coefficients for the explanatory variables included in \mathbf{X}_i , and v_1 , v_2 and v_3 are threshold values that are estimated along with $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. The $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ coefficient estimates are transformed into marginal effects which relate the change in the predicted probability that the survey response (y) falls within a given category due to a change in explanatory variables. These marginal effects are calculated as the averages response, meaning that the change in the predicted probability of a given response for a one unit change in a single variable is calculated many times, with all other variables set to all combinations of observed values. This effect is then averaged over all of these calculations to obtain the average response of the predicted probability.

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